

Industry wise Herd behaviour in the Indian Stock Market with Special Reference to National Stock Exchange

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Abstract : *Purpose* of the article is to examine the presence of herd behaviour at sectoral level in the National Stock Exchange (NSE) of India.

Design The study is empirical in nature. The most popular model proposed by Chang et al. (2000) has been employed to detect herd formation in each sector. Seventeen major sectors except media and realty sectors have been considered along with NIFTY50 constituent companies consisting daily, weekly and monthly observations of closing prices of companies constituting sectoral indices and NIFTY50 for the period from 2006 to 2021.

Results revealed insignificant evidence of herd behaviour at sectoral level and found significant evidence of anti-herd behaviour especially in the daily return data. The results of the study assist investors to develop their trading strategies in the volatile market conditions.

Further researches may include more variables or conduct a study on specific index like large cap or small cap stocks and may also include SENSEX in the study for achieving better results.

Keywords : Herd behaviour, Cross Sectional Absolute Deviation, NSE, Sector-wise Herding.

I. Introduction

Most of the previous studies are found survey-based in India primarily detecting the behavioral biases that affect the investment decision by investors. Still, this is either insufficient or non-conclusive in explaining the impact of any precise behavioral bias on the Indian stock market. Therefore, the present study has

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tried to analyse the market-wide herd behaviour using NIFTY50 data and sector-wise data. For this purpose, the companies whose data is completely and consistently available for the whole period of study are selected. Nofsinger and Sias (1999) define herding as a group of investors trading in the same direction over a period of time. Herd behaviour can be explained in two different ways, i.e., rational and irrational. "Irrational herd can be explained as a tendency of investors irrationally ignoring their own analysis and information and conforming to the market consensus, even if they do not agree with that" (Christie & Huang, 1995). The reason to detect the herd behaviour from sector point of view is that the information dispersed at the sectoral level generally provide basis for asset managers' suggestions, financial analyst's analysis and investors' decisions (Demirer et al., 2010). Mispricing of securities may occur due to herd behaviour of investors which makes the stock markets inefficient. The remainder portion is organized in following sections. Section 2 presents review of literature. Section 3 describes the Research design and data. Section 4 presents methodology. Section 5 reports the empirical evidences of the presence of the herd behaviour at industry level in the Indian stock market and section 6 presents the summary and conclusions.

II. Review of Literature

Lakonishok, Shleifer, & Vishny (1992) recommended a quantitative approach to examine whether herd behaviour exhibited between pension fund managers and results found that there was no evidence of herd behaviour between pension fund managers. Later, Christie & Huang (1995) proposed a new method called Cross Sectional Standard Deviation (CSSD) as a measure of dispersion to examine herd behaviour by observing how individual stock returns change towards the return of the market in large price movements and the results failed to detect herd behaviour. Chang, Cheng, & Khorana (2000) developed a new method based on the Cross-Sectional Return Dispersion (CSAD) which an extended version of CSSD found no significant evidence of herd behaviour in developed markets. Rýza Demirer & Kutan (2006) investigated the herd behaviour at sector level in both Shanghai and Shenzhen stock exchange in China and found no evidence of herd behaviour at sector level. Many researchers around different countries tried to examine the presence of herd behaviour in different markets, for instance, commodities market (Klotzle et al., 2019; Babalos et al., 2015), cryptocurrency market (Kaiser & Stockl, 2019; Klotzle et al., 2019; Ballis & Drakos 2019, mutual fund (Cai et al., 2019; Deng et al., 2018). Many of the researchers

conducted study on examining the presence of herd behaviour in the stock markets specifically during extreme market conditions (Adem 2020; Satish & Padmasree 2018; Deng et al., 2018; Zheng et al., 2017; Mobarek et al., 2014; Jlassi & Bensaida, 2014; Abbi et al., 2014; Lan, 2014; Al-Shboul, 2013; Kostakis et al., 2011; Bowe & Domuta, 2004; Hwang & Salmon, 2004). Some researchers found that United States stock market is free from herd formation (Chang et al., 2000); (Chiang & Zheng, 2010). Significant evidence of herd behaviour was found in South Korean and Taiwanese stock markets (Chang et al., 2000); Dubai, Kuwait, Qatar and Saudi Arabian stock markets (Balcilar et al., 2014); Indian and Chinese stock markets (Lao & Singh, 2011); Asian markets (Chiang & Zheng, 2010). Some researcher found significant evidence of herd behaviour in the stock market during extreme market movements (Tan et al. 2008); (Caparrelli et al., 2004).

III. Research Design

The present study is empirical in nature. Under this study, the presence of herd behaviour in the Indian stock market has been investigated.

Sample and Data Collection

In order to examine the existence of herd behaviour in the Indian Stock Market with special reference to National Stock Exchange, data of closing prices of companies constituting sectors of NSE has been extracted from PROWESS database. The time period has been considered from 2006 to 2021 for the study and the data has been extracted on September 29, 2022.

This period has been considered due to wide fluctuations observed during this time-period because of sub-prime crisis as well as economic and political events took place in the country and around the globe. However, the list of firms for each sector as well as the name of the sectors is obtained from National Stock Exchange official website. Thus, to test the herd behaviour in the Indian stock market stock return data and sector-wise return data both has been used. Out of 17 sectors, two sectors are eliminated from the study due to non-availability of the data namely Media and Realty sectors.

Hypotheses

H_0 : Herd behaviour does not exist in the Indian stock market with special reference to sectors of National Stock Exchange.

IV. Methodology for detecting Herd Behaviour in the Indian Stock Market

Reviewed literatures suggested two extensively used measures to detect herd behaviour. One model is proposed by Christie and Huang (1995) and another one is proposed by Chang, Cheng and Khorana (2000). Christie and Huang (1995) proposed cross sectional standard dispersion (CSSD) model and Chang et al. (2000) proposed cross sectional absolute deviation (CSAD) model which is a modified model of Christie and Huang (1995) method. It has been noticed in the findings of Lux (1995), Lux and Marchesi (1999), (Mertzanis and Allam, 2018) that herd behaviour is capable of introducing non-linear dynamics in the market and CSSD tends to be sensitive to outliers. Therefore, to overcome this concerned issue, Chang et al. (2000) proposed CSAD model which is also followed by present study as follows :

$$CSAD_t = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |R_{i,t} - R_m| \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

where $CSAD_t$ indicates the distance from the market average return, how much of the individual stock returns are dispersed around the average return, N defines the total number of stocks in the NIFTY50 index, $R_{i,t}$ denotes the return of stock i on day t and the $R_{m,t}$ is the cross-sectional average market return at day t . Presence of herd behaviour has been examined using modified regression model following Lee et al. (2013) study as per following equation :

$$CSAD_t = \alpha + \beta_1 |R_{m,t}| + \beta_2 R_{m,t}^2 \quad \text{Equation (2)}$$

where, $|R_{m,t}|$ is the absolute market return at day t , used to account for the magnitude only and not the direction of the stock market; $R_{m,t}^2$ is the squared value of the equally weighted portfolio and captures the non-linear relationship that would arise because of the herding behaviour in the market. It is based on the rationale that under normal conditions, it is anticipated that the return dispersion and market volatility shares a linear relationship. However, during periods of relatively large price movements in which market participants are more likely to herd around indicators such as the average consensus of all market opinions, it becomes more likely that the relation between CSAD and the average market return tend to be nonlinear. Thus, a nonlinear market return, $R_{m,t}^2$ has been included in the test equations. According to Chang et al. (2000), a significant negative non-linear coefficient β_2 confirms the presence of herd behaviour since

it reflects the phenomenon that during periods of extreme market movements, a negative, nonlinear relationship between return dispersion and $R_{m,t}^2$ exists; otherwise, a statistically positive β_2 represents no evidence of herd behaviour in the market.

Regression coefficients have been estimated separately for positive and negative market returns to investigate the asymmetry in bullish and bearish market conditions, precisely, using the following models :

$$CSAD_t^{Up} = \alpha + \beta_1^{Up} |R_{m,t}^{Up}| + \beta_2^{Up} (R_{m,t}^{Up})^2 \quad \text{Equation (3)}$$

$$CSAD_t^{Down} = \alpha + \beta_1^{Down} |R_{m,t}^{Down}| + \beta_2^{Down} (R_{m,t}^{Down})^2 \quad \text{Equation (4)}$$

Where, $CSAD_t^{Up}$ and $CSAD_t^{Down}$ are the Cross Sectional Absolute Deviation at day t corresponding to returns during rising and declining market respectively. $CSAD_t^{Up}$ is calculated when $R_{m,t} > 0$ and $CSAD_t^{Down}$ is calculated when $R_{m,t} < 0$. $R_{m,t}^{Up}$ and $R_{m,t}^{Down}$ denotes equal weighted portfolio returns during bull and bear market condition on t and $(R_{m,t}^{Up})^2$ $(R_{m,t}^{Down})^2$ is the squared value of the equal-weighted portfolio to examine the non-linearity in market returns during rising market declining market.

V. Analysis and Interpretation

Sector wise detection of herd behaviour

Table-1 presents a summarized result of regression equation for the specified sectors during the whole period of study for daily, weekly and monthly data. The CSAD model included 17 sectors data of NIFTY to test the presence of herd behaviour towards market consensus. According to the CSAD model a negative and statistically significant coefficient of squared market return (β_2) confirms the existence of herd behaviour in the market.

The empirical findings of Table-IV clearly shows that the probability value of F-statistics (0.000) for regression equation is valid and statistically significant at 1% and 5% level of significance for all the three data frequencies. The values

Table-1 : Regression Results According to CSAD Model for the Whole Period

Name of Sectors	Type of Data	β_1	β_2	F - statistics	Adjusted R^2
AUTO	Daily	0.0695 (0.000)	0.0594 (0.000)	2110.352 (0.000)	0.5156
	Weekly	-0.0239 (0.6233)	0.0405 (0.000)	235.80054 (0.000)	0.3605
	Monthly	0.2129 (0.042)	0.0008 (0.822)	13.5565 (0.000)	0.1167
BANK	Daily	-0.1498 (0.000)	0.0772 (0.000)	4597.300 (0.000)	0.6987
	Weekly	-0.3016 (0.000)	0.0601 (0.000)	366.8400 (0.000)	0.4676
	Monthly	0.2462 (0.064)	0.0043 (0.245)	21.5534 (0.000)	0.1779
CONSUMER DURABLES	Daily	0.2494 (0.000)	0.0459 (0.000)	8923.837 (0.000)	0.8182
	Weekly	0.0401 (0.267)	0.0343 (0.000)	1554.524 (0.000)	0.7886
	Monthly	0.0014 (0.992)	0.0217 (0.000)	74.7976 (0.000)	0.4372
FINANCIAL SERVICES	Daily	-0.0258 (0.0868)	0.0690 (0.000)	5245.334 (0.000)	0.7257
	Weekly	-0.1674 (0.0048)	0.0523 (0.000)	398.6543 (0.000)	0.4884
	Monthly	0.6125 (0.000)	-0.0064 (0.104)	27.1384 (0.000)	0.2158
FAST MOVING CONSUMER GOODS	Daily	0.1716 (0.000)	0.0746 (0.000)	8102.773 (0.000)	0.8034
	Weekly	0.0261 (0.532)	0.0649 (0.000)	1027.716 (0.000)	0.7114
	Monthly	-0.0745 (0.644)	0.0436 (0.000)	60.0316 (0.000)	0.3832
FINANCIAL SERVICES 25/50	Daily	0.0342 (0.0478)	0.0739 (0.000)	3421.477 (0.000)	0.6331
	Weekly	0.1630 (0.000)	0.0305 (0.000)	254.898 (0.000)	0.3787
	Monthly	0.5949 (0.000)	-0.0071* (0.035)	30.7142 (0.000)	0.2382

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FINANCIAL SERVICES EX-BANK	Daily	0.1574 (0.000)	0.0604 (0.000)	3834.145 (0.000)	0.6592
	Weekly	0.0647 (0.219)	0.0387 (0.000)	381.768 (0.000)	0.4776
	Monthly	0.5493 (0.000)	-0.0041 (0.161)	42.7195 (0.000)	0.3051
HEALTHCARE	Daily	0.0387 (0.033)	0.1103 (0.000)	4404.061 (0.000)	0.6896
	Weekly	0.1485 (0.015)	0.0477 (0.000)	338.5351 (0.000)	0.4476
	Monthly	0.3595 (0.018)	0.0026 (0.674)	21.2173 (0.000)	0.1754
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY	Daily	-0.1638 (0.000)	0.1049 (0.000)	2430.228 (0.000)	0.5507
	Weekly	0.2334 (0.000)	0.0219 (0.000)	135.0371 (0.000)	0.2435
	Monthly	0.4267 (0.001)	-0.0043 (0.491)	21.7926 (0.000)	0.1796
METAL	Daily	-0.0469 (0.000)	0.0526 (0.000)	4308.166 (0.000)	0.6849
	Weekly	-0.2254 (0.000)	0.0420 (0.000)	364.8219 (0.000)	0.4662
	Monthly	0.1971 (0.081)	0.0021 (0.415)	17.3174 (0.000)	0.1466
OIL & GAS	Daily	0.1104 (0.000)	0.0634 (0.000)	3238.746 (0.000)	0.6203
	Weekly	-0.0042 (0.935)	0.0472 (0.000)	400.3085 (0.000)	0.4895
	Monthly	0.2581 (0.052)	0.0059 (0.240)	29.4442 (0.000)	0.2304
PHARMA	Daily	0.0559 (0.001)	0.1116 (0.000)	5780.600 (0.000)	0.7446
	Weekly	0.3110 (0.001)	-0.0637** (0.000)	79.7704 (0.000)	0.1590
	Monthly	0.4498 (0.006)	0.0048 (0.511)	34.8925 (0.000)	0.2629
PRIVATE BANK	Daily	-0.1146 (0.000)	0.0673 (0.000)	5991.664 (0.000)	0.7514
	Weekly	-0.1942 (0.000)	0.0441 (0.000)	608.8650 (0.000)	0.5934
	Monthly	0.2786 (0.025)	0.0042 (0.168)	32.5162 (0.000)	0.2491

(Contd...)

PUBLIC SERVICE UNDERTAKING BANK	Daily	0.0014 (0.913)	0.0404 (0.000)	1895.675 (0.000)	0.4887
	Weekly	-0.1880 (0.000)	0.0349 (0.000)	264.1535 (0.000)	0.3872
	Monthly	0.0835 (0.494)	0.0044 (0.306)	11.9479 (0.000)	0.1033
MIDSMALL FINANCIAL SERVICES	Daily	0.0709 (0.000)	0.0819 (0.000)	2673.353 (0.000)	0.5742
	Weekly	0.0810 (0.103)	0.0419 (0.000)	440.1244 (0.000)	0.5132
	Monthly	0.3805 (0.000)	-0.0016 (0.540)	29.9478 (0.000)	0.2335
MIDSMALL HEALTHCARE	Daily	0.0528 (0.003)	0.1043 (0.000)	3801.792 (0.000)	0.6573
	Weekly	0.0242 (0.667)	0.0561 (0.000)	311.3591 (0.000)	0.4270
	Monthly	0.2599 (0.078)	0.0068 (0.297)	23.8189 (0.000)	0.1937
MIDSMALL INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND TELECOM	Daily	0.0885 (0.000)	0.0648 (0.000)	105.872 (0.000)	0.4474
	Weekly	0.3938 (0.000)	0.0011 (0.729)	131.5464 (0.000)	0.2387
	Monthly	0.2902 (0.000)	-0.0019 (0.426)	19.2464 (0.000)	0.1611

Source : Eviews Output

* and ** means statistically significant at 5% and 1% level respectively.

of adjusted R^2 are higher in the daily data followed by weekly and monthly data respectively signifying the appropriateness of the regression model. The main focus of Table-IV is on the coefficient of squared market return (β_2) because the CCK (2000) model says that herd behaviour is present in the market when the coefficient β_2 is negative and statistically significant at 1% and 5% level of significance. The results showed that the coefficient of β_2 is positive and statistically significant at both 5% and 1% level of significance for all the sectors in the daily data which implies anti-herd behaviour in the daily market movement during the whole period. These sectoral based findings are consistent with the individual stock return based findings. This implies that the investors do not follow herd take investment decisions rationally and do not follow the other investors. In the weekly data also except Pharma and Midsmall IT & Telecom sectors the coefficient β_2 is positive and statistically significant which

also supports anti-herd behaviour in the Indian stock market. The coefficient of β_2 found negative and significant for the pharma sector in the weekly observations which infers that investment decisions in the pharmaceuticals industry are rational and do not follow market consensus as far as weekly data is concerned. At the same time, in the monthly data only FMCG sectors have positive and statistically significant β_2 coefficient which implies that investors follow their own belief and information while investing in FMCG sector in the monthly observations. The coefficient β_1 implies magnitude of change in the value of $CSAD_t$ for every increase in the value of absolute market return. It has also been observed that the coefficient β_2 is higher in the daily data than weekly and monthly data so it can be interpreted that anti-herd behaviour is prominently high in the daily frequency data during the whole period of study. As most of the sectors do not exhibit the existence of herd behaviour (except Pharma and Financial Services 25/50) so the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Thus, the Indian stock market is found efficient industry wise and the results are similar to the individual return data.

Table-2 presents the summarized result of regression equation for all the specified sectors during the bull market conditions for daily, weekly and monthly data. The empirical findings clearly show that the probability value of F-statistics (0.000) for regression equation is valid and statistically significant at 1% and 5% level of significance for all the three data frequencies. The values of adjusted R^2 are higher in the daily data followed by weekly and monthly data respectively signifying the appropriateness of the regression model. The main focus of Table-V is on the coefficient of squared market return (β_2) because the CCK (2000) model says that herd behaviour is present in the market when the coefficient β_2 is negative and statistically significant at 1% and 5% level of significance. Thus, any change in squared market return makes the value of $CSAD$ decrease by the magnitude of β_2 when herd behaviour exists. This can be said that a significant decrease in the value of $CSAD$ refers that investment decisions taken by investors are close to market return movements or investors imitate the market consensus.

The coefficient β_2 is negative and statistically significant for the Automobile, Information Technology and Oil & Gas sectors only for the daily return data. However, the β_2 coefficient is significantly negative at both 1% and 5% level of significance and the β_2 coefficient for Automobile and Information Technology is negatively significant at 5% level only. When it comes to weekly data, the β_2 coefficient has found to be statistically significant and positive for the Auto and

Table-2 : Regression Results According to CSAD Model During Bull Market Conditions

Name of Sectors	Type of Data	β_1	β_2	F - statistics	Adjusted R ²
AUTO	Daily	0.3659 (0.000)	-0.0071 (0.037)	410.1091 (0.000)	0.2786
	Weekly	0.0332 (0.000)	0.0169 (0.000)	157.3564 (0.000)	0.2729
	Monthly	-0.0418 (0.693)	0.0069 (0.140)	4.2437 (0.000)	0.0572
BANK	Daily	0.2261 (0.000)	0.0036 (0.161)	311.0932 (0.000)	0.2301
	Weekly	0.1974 (0.000)	0.0005 (0.863)	63.7989 (0.000)	0.2152
	Monthly	-0.0917 (0.410)	0.0047 (0.220)	0.9898 (0.000)	-0.0002
CONSUMER DURABLES	Daily	0.4634 (0.000)	-0.0068 (0.245)	484.4276 (0.000)	0.3079
	Weekly	0.3422 (0.000)	-0.0058 (0.103)	52.4612 (0.000)	0.1763
	Monthly	0.1786 (0.0197)	0.0006 (0.808)	12.3997 (0.000)	0.1543
FINANCIAL SERVICES	Daily	0.2873 (0.000)	0.0032 (0.322)	380.1942 (0.000)	0.2632
	Weekly	0.2701 (0.000)	-0.0025 (0.467)	71.7728 (0.000)	0.2307
	Monthly	0.2359 (0.006)	-0.0032 (0.287)	10.055 (0.000)	0.1424
FAST MOVING CONSUMER GOODS	Daily	0.3612 (0.000)	0.0140 (0.057)	371.4723 (0.000)	0.2561
	Weekly	0.3103 (0.000)	-0.0114 (0.312)	35.2048 (0.000)	0.1271
	Monthly	0.0392 (0.763)	0.0058 (0.558)	2.4762 (0.000)	0.0255
FINANCIAL SERVICES 25/50	Daily	0.3142 (0.000)	0.0037 (0.308)	409.5662 (0.000)	0.2749
	Weekly	0.2688 (0.000)	0.0015 (0.719)	88.8931 (0.000)	0.2743
	Monthly	0.2073 (0.014)	0.0003 (0.932)	19.9203 (0.000)	0.2459
FINANCIAL SERVICES EX- BANK	Daily	0.4044 (0.000)	0.0081 (0.108)	548.0619 (0.000)	0.3378
	Weekly	0.2648 (0.000)	-0.0050 (0.226)	46.7115 (0.000)	0.1605
	Monthly	0.2029 (0.026)	0.0006 (0.865)	18.3237 (0.000)	0.2315

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HEALTHCARE	Daily	0.3134 (0.000)	0.0079 (0.158)	340.0826 (0.000)	0.2400
	Weekly	0.2648 (0.000)	-0.0050 (0.226)	46.7115 (0.000)	0.1605
	Monthly	-0.0111 (0.918)	0.0071 (0.186)	3.9915* (0.0218)	0.0520
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY	Daily	0.3006 (0.000)	-0.0074 (0.047)	295.3380 (0.000)	0.2187
	Weekly	0.1462 (0.035)	0.0058 (0.467)	24.3377 (0.000)	0.0919
	Monthly	-0.0571 (0.577)	0.0111 (0.031)	9.8035 (0.000)	0.1424
METAL	Daily	0.2426 (0.000)	5.4333 (0.9859)	284.9421 (0.000)	0.2141
	Weekly	0.1226 (0.016)	0.0056 (0.127)	42.3520 (0.000)	0.1591
	Monthly	0.1651 (0.055)	-0.0026 (0.307)	3.1255 (0.048)	0.0404
OIL & GAS	Daily	0.3720 (0.000)	-0.0125 (0.000)	317.5335 (0.000)	0.2339
	Weekly	0.2759 (0.000)	-0.0007 (0.885)	62.8617 (0.000)	0.2202
	Monthly	-0.0150 (0.913)	0.0077 (0.253)	3.2967 (0.041)	0.0452
PHARMA	Daily	0.3551 (0.000)	0.0052 (0.370)	397.0852 (0.000)	.2700
	Weekly	0.9992 (0.000)	3.8888 (0.439)	6140 (0.000)	0.9999
	Monthly	0.1338 (0.229)	0.0012 (0.8457)	4.5075 (0.013)	0.0594
PRIVATE BANK	Daily	0.2776 (0.000)	-0.0033 (0.220)	305.063 (0.000)	0.2252
	Weekly	0.1626 (0.000)	0.0041 (0.1459)	65.3406 (0.000)	0.2125
	Monthly	0.0067 (0.929)	0.0027 (0.279)	3.4702 (0.034)	0.0415
PUBLIC SERVICE UNDERTAKING BANK	Daily	0.2306 (0.000)	-0.0011 (0.292)	399.2105 (0.000)	0.2892
	Weekly	0.0946 (0.008)	0.0071 (0.000)	98.6355 (0.000)	0.3258
	Monthly	0.1153 (0.180)	0.0004 (0.888)	9.6472 (0.000)	0.1707

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MIDSMALL FINANCIAL SERVICES	Daily	0.3731 (0.000)	0.0028 (0.536)	403.7158 (0.000)	0.2752
	Weekly	0.3302 (0.000)	0.0005 (0.884)	114.3100 (0.000)	0.3405
	Monthly	0.0922 (0.366)	0.0032 (0.427)	8.7879 (0.000)	0.1271
MIDSMALL HEALTHCARE	Daily	0.4187 (0.000)	0.0086 (0.206)	575.4673 (0.000)	0.3483
	Weekly	0.3059 (0.000)	-0.0047 (0.381)	63.8833 (0.000)	0.2100
	Monthly	-0.1395 (0.2949)	0.0149 (0.025)	5.7712 (0.004)	0.0791
MIDSMALL INFORMATI ON TECHNOLO GY AND TELECOM	Daily	0.4496 (0.000)	-0.0045 (0.454)	478.5390 (0.000)	0.3106
	Weekly	0.3143 (0.000)	-0.0013 (0.8257)	62.4690 (0.000)	0.2077
	Monthly	0.0338 (0.705)	0.0006 (0.772)	0.0837 (0.919)	-0.0244

Source: Eviews * and ** means statistically significant at 5% and 1% level respectively.

PSU sector only. The β_2 coefficient is not statistically significant for rest of the sectors so in respect of weekly observations, it can be infer that Auto and PSU sectors are free from herd behaviour or the investment decisions in these sectors have been rational. At the same time, the β_2 coefficient of monthly data has found to be positive and statistically significant for the IT and Midsmall Health care sectors only at 5% level and insignificant for the rest of the sectors. Thus it can be inferred that the investment decisions in these two sectors have been rational in the monthly frequency data. The coefficient β_1 implies magnitude of change in the value of $CSAD_t$ for every increase in the value of absolute market return. It has also been observed that coefficient β_1 is positive and statistically significant in the daily and weekly data for all the sectors but positively significant for consumer durables, Financial Services, Financial Services 25/50 and Financial Services Ex-Bank sector only in the monthly data which means that value of $CSAD_t$ increases with the magnitude of β_1 coefficient of absolute market return. Thus, the results of bull market data are consistent with the results of whole period data and bear market data that the herd behaviour does not exist in the Indian stock market. The results are inconsistent with the findings of (Lee et al., 2013; Tan et al., 2008). Hence, null hypothesis cannot be rejected and it can be concluded that the investors in India are well informed and do not follow the market consensus.

Table-3 : Regression Results According to CSAD Model During Bear Market Conditions

Name of Sectors	Type of Data	β_1	β_2	F - statistics	Adjusted R ²
AUTO	Daily	0.0088 (0.712)	0.0686 (0.000)	1480.547 (0.000)	0.6161
	Weekly	-0.1481 (0.085)	0.0568 (0.000)	158.9467 (0.000)	0.4552
	Monthly	0.5417 (0.006)	-0.0072 (0.216)	9.4666 (0.000)	0.1711
BANK	Daily	-0.1776 (0.000)	0.0829 (0.000)	3422.916 (0.000)	0.7838
	Weekly	-0.4839 (0.000)	0.0817 (0.000)	275.5385 (0.000)	0.5948
	Monthly	0.6830 (0.003)	-0.0025 (0.670)	18.1258 (0.000)	0.2872
CONSUMER DURABLES	Daily	0.2515 (0.000)	0.0462 (0.000)	5844.970 (0.000)	0.8672
	Weekly	0.1011 (0.099)	0.0337 (0.000)	1000.225 (0.000)	0.8506
	Monthly	0.0558 (0.876)	0.0243 (0.010)	32.1106 (0.000)	0.4929
FINANCIAL SERVICES	Daily	-0.0294 (0.239)	0.0712 (0.000)	3484.610 (0.000)	0.7911
	Weekly	-0.1944 (0.085)	0.0597 (0.000)	233.217 (0.000)	0.5633
	Monthly	1.0364 (0.000)	-0.0142* (0.033)	17.6086 (0.000)	0.2934
FAST MOVING CONSUMER GOODS	Daily	0.1638 (0.000)	0.0754 (0.000)	5285.852 (0.000)	0.8537
	Weekly	0.1378 (0.060)	0.0606 (0.000)	620.0343 (0.000)	0.7737
	Monthly	0.3887 (0.218)	0.0272 (0.072)	31.2075 (0.000)	0.4429
FINANCIAL SERVICES 25/50	Daily	0.0474 (0.104)	0.07673 (0.000)	2153.116 (0.000)	0.7042
	Weekly	0.3298 (0.003)	0.0267 (0.000)	132.9977 (0.000)	0.4184
	Monthly	1.0260 (0.000)	-0.0163** (0.007)	15.8068 (0.000)	0.2886

(Contd...)

FINANCIAL SERVICES EX- BANK	Daily	0.1209 (0.000)	0.0633 (0.000)	2360.506 (0.000)	0.7219
	Weekly	0.0649 (0.516)	0.0425 (0.000)	199.1127 (0.000)	0.5232
	Monthly	1.0000 (0.000)	-0.0126* (0.011)	24.1811 (0.000)	0.3852
HEALTHCARE	Daily	0.0751 (0.012)	0.1113 (0.000)	2833.364 (0.000)	0.7572
	Weekly	0.2763 (0.014)	0.0511 (0.000)	215.8036 (0.000)	0.5482
	Monthly	0.9018 (0.001)	-0.0133 (0.198)	15.644 (0.000)	-0.2679
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY	Daily	-0.2586 (0.000)	0.1296 (0.000)	2150.488 (0.000)	0.6980
	Weekly	0.5440 (0.000)	0.0075 (0.327)	84.5666 (0.000)	0.3106
	Monthly	1.0446 (0.000)	-0.0252* (0.014)	19.3348 (0.000)	0.3064
METAL	Daily	-0.0603 (0.003)	0.0544 (0.000)	2917.910 (0.000)	0.7564
	Weekly	-0.2224 (0.008)	0.0454 (0.000)	233.5911 (0.000)	0.5408
	Monthly	0.4496 (0.040)	-0.0014 (0.7523)	11.4981 (0.000)	0.1926
OIL & GAS	Daily	0.1617 (0.000)	0.0649 (0.000)	2281.900 (0.000)	0.7071
	Weekly	0.0484 (0.586)	0.0489 (0.000)	245.0812 (0.000)	0.5534
	Monthly	0.6838 (0.002)	-0.0060 (0.435)	22.1563 (0.000)	0.3150
PHARMA	Daily	0.0699 (0.011)	0.1137 (0.000)	3902.082 (0.000)	0.8106
	Weekly	-1.0000 (0.000)	-8.1000** (0.000)	5.8111 (0.000)	1.0000
	Monthly	1.1153 (0.000)	-0.0166 (0.192)	23.9446 (0.000)	0.3704
PRIVATE BANK	Daily	-0.1559 (0.000)	0.0714 (0.000)	4379.548 (0.000)	0.8239
	Weekly	-0.1817 (0.037)	0.0469 (0.000)	348.1875 (0.000)	0.6617
	Monthly	0.6877 (0.005)	-0.0022 (0.683)	18.8094 (0.000)	0.3219

(Contd...)

PUBLIC SERVICE UNDERTAKING BANK	Daily	-0.1694 (0.000)	0.0703 (0.000)	3077.906 (0.000)	0.7542
	Weekly	-0.5385 (0.000)	0.0716 (0.000)	331.8463 (0.000)	0.6072
	Monthly	-0.0348 (0.871)	0.0122 (0.135)	8.0236 (0.000)	0.1179
MIDSMALL FINANCIAL SERVICES	Daily	0.0452 (0.164)	0.0878 (0.000)	1649.588 (0.000)	0.6416
	Weekly	0.0018 (0.982)	0.0555 (0.000)	300.2158 (0.000)	0.6036
	Monthly	0.6787 (0.000)	-0.0073 (0.077)	18.5081 (0.000)	0.2992
MIDSMALL HEALTHCARE	Daily	-0.0516 (0.081)	0.1155 (0.000)	2394.080 (0.000)	0.7253
	Weekly	0.0255 (0.801)	0.0658 (0.000)	187.062 (0.000)	0.5089
	Monthly	0.7644 (0.005)	-0.0082 (0.462)	16.9168 (0.000)	0.2898
MIDSMALL INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND TELECOM	Daily	-0.0529 (0.113)	0.0779 (0.000)	972.8629 (0.000)	0.5133
	Weekly	0.5407 (0.000)	-0.0042 (0.420)	64.4798 (0.000)	0.2591
	Monthly	0.4196 (0.009)	-0.0054 (0.179)	7.4834 (0.001)	0.1441

Source: Eviews

* mean significant at 5% and ** mean significant at 1% level.

Table-3 above shows the summarized regression results applying CSAD model when the market is in declining state for daily, weekly and monthly data. The empirical findings show that the probability of F-statistics (0.000) is statistically significant and valid at 1% and 5% level of significance for daily, weekly and monthly data signifying the validity of the regression model. The values of adjusted R^2 are higher in the daily data followed by weekly and monthly data respectively signifying the appropriateness of the regression model. The main focus of Table-VI is on the coefficient of squared market return (β_2) because the CCK (2000) model says that herd behaviour is present in the market when the coefficient β_2 is negative and statistically significant at 1% and 5% level of significance. Thus, any change in squared market return makes the value of CSAD decrease by the magnitude of β_2 when herd behaviour exists. The results showed that the coefficient of β_2 is positive and statistically significant at both 5% and 1% level of significance for all the sectors in the daily data which implies

anti-herd behaviour in the daily market movement when the market is declining. This signifies that the investors take investment decisions rationally and do not follow the other investors. In the weekly data also except two sectors (Pharma, Midsmall IT and Telecom) the coefficient β_2 is positive and statistically significant which also supports anti-herd behaviour in the Indian stock market. At the same time, in the monthly data except five sectors (Financial Services, Financial Services 25/50, Financial Services Ex-Bank, IT and Pharma) the p-value of others' β_2 coefficient is not statistically significant whether it be positive or negative. The regression results of Financial Services 25/50 and Pharma sector exhibit the existence of herd behaviour at both 5% and 1% levels of significance. However, the results of Financial Services, Financial Services Ex-Bank and IT sectors found negative and statistically significant at 5% level only. The coefficient β_1 implies magnitude of change in the value of $CSAD_t^{DOWN}$ for every increase in the value of absolute market return during bear market conditions. The coefficient β_1 has found to be positive and significant for majority sectors. It has also been observed that the coefficient β_2 is higher in daily data than weekly and monthly data so it can be concluded that anti-herd behaviour is more prevalent in the daily frequency data during declining movement of the market. As the majority of sectors do not exhibit the existence of herd behaviour, so the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. It can be concluded that Indian stock market is efficient during bear phase for the study period 2006 to 2021 and investors take investment decision rationally.

VI. Conclusion

The existence of herd behaviour towards the market consensus has been investigated using sector wise individual stock return data. In addition, sector-wise herd behaviour has been tested using daily, weekly and monthly data for both individual stock return and sectoral index returns. In order to test the herd behaviour CSAD model has been applied.

The CSAD model which is a non-linear model exhibited the non-existence of herd behaviour in the Indian stock market for the whole period as well as when the market is in bull and bear phase, especially in the daily data. When it comes to weekly data Pharma sector has shown the existence of herd behaviour in whole period and bear phase. While Financial Services 25/50 sector has displayed the existence of herd behaviour for the monthly observations. The results are consistent with Kanojia et al. (2020), Satish and Padmasree (2018) and Prosad et al. (2012), Demirer and Kutan (2006), Kumar et al. (2016), Dutta et al. (2016) and Ganesh et al. (2016), who recently tested the herd behaviour in the Indian stock

market and concluded that Indian equity market is usually free from sectoral herd behaviour even when some level of herd behaviour has been depicted. But the empirical findings contradict with the findings of Lao and Singh (2011), Yang et al. (2015), Ramadan (2015), Caparrelli et al. (2004), Balcilar et al. (2014), Kapusuzoglu (2011), and Yasir (2018) who found that the herd behaviour exist in the stock market especially in the extreme market conditions. Even if the magnitude of the coefficient of anti-herd behaviour decreases in the weekly and monthly data, there are statistically significant findings which show that herd behaviour was not present in the weekly and monthly data. Therefore, the findings support the validity of rational asset pricing models.

Behavioural finance is still evolving in emerging markets as studies have majorly focused on developed markets. This research will surely be advantageous for those investors who want to understand and study on the psychology of Indian investors and for the regulatory authorities which can take remedial measures for this specific behavioural bias. Future researches may include the other stock markets in India for more advanced results and also check the impact of stock markets of other countries on the herd behaviour of Indian stock market.

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